

Research Article

Constructing an Integrated Irrigation System for Non-Granary Farmers in Kelantan

Mohamad Afham Azmin¹, Muhammad Alif Aiqal Ramli², Muhamad Khairun Annam Mohd Asri³, Nor Halida Haziaton Mohd Noor⁴, Azmahani Yaacob @ Othman⁵, Siti Nur Zahirah Omar⁶, Nik Mohd Shamim Nik Mohd Zainordin⁷, and Mariam Setapa^{8,*}

¹ Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; afhamashri@gmail.com

² Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; mhd.alifaiqal@gmail.com

³ Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; muhamadkhairunannam97@gmail.com

⁴ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; halida552@uitm.edu.my

⁵ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; azma928@uitm.edu.my

⁶ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; sitinurzahirah@uitm.edu.my

⁷ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; nikshamim@uitm.edu.my

⁸ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; maria135@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2151-7909>)

* Correspondence: maria135@uitm.edu.my; +6013 724 2641

Abstract: Water management is an important element in paddy production. Water management can increase the productivity level, thereby increasing the income of farmers. Irrigation systems should be a relevant agent to give solutions to the increasing demand for food, and the development, sustainability and productivity of the agricultural sector. The design, management, and operation of irrigation systems are crucial factors to achieve an efficient use of water resources and success in the production of crops. Efficient water management is one of the key elements in the successful operation and management of irrigation schemes. This study examined the weakness of irrigation and drainage systems in the non-granary area in Banggol Judah, Machang, Kelantan. Besides, the report identifies key issues, including non-supportive government policies for non-granary areas, operational inefficiencies in existing irrigation systems, and ineffective utilization of agricultural water. The proposed dam irrigation system is described in detail, highlighting its functional specifications, novelty, and uniqueness tailored to the local context. The study also addresses potential commercialization, indicating a focus on corporate social responsibility rather than direct innovation for profit. In conclusion, the report emphasizes the critical role of innovative irrigation technologies, such as the dam irrigation system, in achieving sustainable water management and climate change adaptation in agriculture. The system's precision, adaptability, and resource efficiency position it as a promising solution for the future of paddy cultivation in Machang and beyond. The abstract encapsulates the report's journey from identifying challenges to proposing a transformative solution, reflecting a commitment to a resilient and productive agricultural future.

Keywords: Water irrigation; Paddy field; Non-granary area; Innovation; Agriculture

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1. INTRODUCTION

Water required by crops is supplied by nature in the form of precipitation, but when it becomes scarce or its distribution does not coincide with demand peaks, it is then necessary to supply it

artificially, by irrigation. Several irrigation methods are available, and the selection of one depends on factors such as water availability, crop, soil characteristics, land topography, and associated cost. In the near future, irrigated agriculture will need to produce two-thirds of the increase in food products required by a larger population. The growing dependence on irrigated agriculture coincides with an accelerated competition for water and increased awareness of unintended negative consequences of poor design and management. Optimum management of available water resources at farm level is needed because of increasing demands, limited resources, water table variation in space and time, and soil contamination (Kumar and Singh, 2003). Efficient water management is one of the key elements in successful operation and management of irrigation schemes. Irrigation water management involves determining when to irrigate, the amount of water to apply at each irrigation event and during each stage of the plant, and operating and maintaining the irrigation system. The main management objective is to manage the production system for the port without compromising the environment and in agreement with water availability. A major management activity involves irrigation scheduling or determining when and how much water to apply, considering the irrigation method and other field characteristics. Under limitations in water availability, it is required to develop new irrigation scheduling approaches focused on to ensure optimal use of available water, and not based on full crop water requirements. The determination of these efficient and effective irrigation schedules requires the accurate determination of water requirements for the main crops, in order to assist the farmers in deciding when and how much to irrigate their crops. Irrigation technology has made significant advances in recent years. However, in many regions these advances are not yet available at the farm stage. Modernized irrigation systems at farm level implies selecting the appropriate irrigation system and strategy according to the water availability, the characteristics of climate, soil and crop, the economic and social circumstances, and the constraints of the distribution system. Supplemental irrigation is frequently required during extended periods of drought throughout the crop growing season to avoid water stress and yield limitations. Current agricultural water concerns, as well as the need to reduce input costs in farming operations, underline the importance of developing smart watering techniques for optimal water allocation, natural resource conservation, and increased profitability. With this goal in mind, water networks and irrigation systems have been modernized in many countries. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), irrigation of crops uses 70% of the available freshwater. Therefore, efficient use of water for irrigation and increased efficiency of irrigation systems are key factors enabling sustainable water management and adaptation to climate change. The initiatives taken to improve the efficiency of water use have become necessary, especially in those areas where water is the most limiting factor in plant production.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

2.1 Non-supportive by Government for Non-granary Area in Machang

This study identifies the division of the farming area into two main categories: the granary area and the non-granary area. The granary area is officially recognized by the government as the primary zone for paddy production, Conversely, the non-granary area lacks this official recognition as highlighted by Siwar, Nor, Muhammad, and Golam (2014). The granary areas garner more attention due to their modern infrastructure, facilitating frequent planting. Additionally, these regions are officially designated for rice cultivation under the national food security policy. In contrast, non-granary areas are less equipped, have a lower planting frequency, and are susceptible to conversion to other crops. Nevertheless, both areas contribute significantly to the nation's rice self-sufficiency level. Insufficient government support is evident for non-granary areas. These regions lack the backing and resources provided to granary areas, which receive attention and investment in modern infrastructure, contributing to a higher frequency of planting. In contrast, non-granary areas face challenges such as limited support, lower cultivation frequency, and a lack of protection for rice fields that could

potentially be converted to other crops. The absence of substantial government support in these non-granary areas hinders their agricultural development and reduces their ability to contribute effectively to national food security objectives.

2.2 Operational Inefficiency of Irrigation Systems

Irrigation typically relies on adequate water resources, primarily sourced from rivers and rainfall. Despite Malaysia's abundance of water, specific dry months (May-August) can lead to decreased water levels, resulting in what is known as "agricultural drought." To maintain a consistent water supply during these periods, it is crucial for all irrigation schemes to operate at optimal performance. Unfortunately, some of these irrigation systems fall short of meeting the expected standards. For instance, in Machang, certain areas engaged in rice farming lack a proper irrigation system to channel water effectively. The shift towards mechanization in rice farming, particularly the adoption of direct seeding techniques, has significantly affected the demand for irrigation water. It is technically impractical to meet the increasingly individualized water demands of mechanized farms through gravity-based, surface-flow systems like those supported in this project. Because the project cannot fine-tune for water deliveries, the canals in general deliver more water per hectare than necessary. To gain control over the quantity and timing of water, farmers in the Machang district require financial support to construct a network of water channels referred to as "system dams" to expedite the rice seeding process.

2.3 Ineffective Utilization of Agricultural Water

Growing competition for water resources in these sectors is already affecting agriculture in Machang. This issue is expected to worsen, primarily due to the rapid expansion of the domestic economy. The increasing water scarcity and the interconnectedness of water usage sectors are driving Machang towards the development of an integrated irrigation system. This system aims to provide adequate water supply to areas lacking sufficient resources for rice cultivation. Concerns about water quality, along with the heightened emphasis on water conservation and protection, are also on the rise. Despite agriculture accounting for approximately 68% of total water consumption in Machang, irrigation efficiency is at best 50% in larger schemes and less than 40% in smaller ones. Moreover, there is a lack of irrigated water recycling. All these factors pose significant challenges to the long-term sustainability of water resources.

3. PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

Embarking on the construction of a dam irrigation system for paddy fields marks a transformative step in advancing agricultural practices. This innovative system is meticulously designed to cater specifically to the unique requirements of paddy cultivation, promising a paradigm shift in water management and crop yield optimization. The primary objective of the dam irrigation system is to address water scarcity challenges and enhance the overall efficiency of rice farming. With a focus on sustainable water management, the system allows for precise control and distribution of water throughout the paddy fields, ensuring optimal conditions for crop growth at every stage of the cultivation cycle. The construction process involves the integration of state-of-the-art technology, enabling farmers to regulate water levels with precision. This innovative system minimizes water wastage and promotes resource conservation, contributing to environmental sustainability. As the dam takes shape, it becomes a vital component of the agricultural landscape, seamlessly blending functionality with the natural surroundings. The project not only aims to boost agricultural productivity but also seeks to empower farmers with a reliable and eco-friendly solution, ushering in a new era of efficiency and prosperity in paddy cultivation. The dam irrigation system represents a

significant investment in the future of sustainable agriculture, promising increased yields and a more resilient food production system.

Figure 1. The dam irrigation system.

4. FUNCTIONAL SPECIFICATION OF PRODUCT INNOVATION

The functional dam irrigation system represents a pinnacle of product innovation in the realm of agricultural technology. This cutting-edge system is engineered to provide a seamless and efficient solution for water management in various contexts, particularly in paddy fields. At its core, the dam irrigation system is a testament to innovation, incorporating advanced technologies to optimize the distribution and utilization of water resources. Its functional design ensures precision in water control, allowing farmers to adapt to the specific needs of paddy cultivation throughout the entire growth cycle. This innovative product goes beyond traditional irrigation methods, introducing a level of sophistication that not only addresses water scarcity challenges but also enhances overall agricultural productivity. With its smart features and intuitive controls, the dam irrigation system empowers farmers to make informed decisions about water allocation, leading to resource conservation and improved yields. Moreover, the product's innovation extends to its environmental impact, promoting sustainability in agriculture. By minimizing water wastage and maximizing efficiency, the dam irrigation system stands as a beacon of progress in the quest for responsible and eco-friendly farming practices. In conclusion, the functional dam irrigation system epitomizes product innovation by seamlessly integrating advanced technology with agricultural needs, fostering a more sustainable and productive future for paddy cultivation and beyond.

5. NOVELTY AND UNIQUENESS OF THE PRODUCT

The dam irrigation system tailored for the Machang Area introduces a unique set of features and innovations that specifically address the agricultural needs of this region, setting it apart in terms of novelty and uniqueness.

1. **Localized Adaptability:** Customized to the specific requirements of the Machang Area, the system demonstrates a localized adaptability that considers the region's unique climate, topography, and soil conditions. This ensures optimal performance and resource utilization tailored to the local agricultural landscape.
2. **Meticulous Water Conservation:** Recognizing the significance of water conservation in the Machang Area, the system incorporates meticulous water-saving mechanisms. It goes beyond traditional irrigation practices by intelligently managing water resources, thereby mitigating the impact of seasonal variations and contributing to sustainable water usage.
3. **Community-Driven Features:** Unique community-driven features foster collaboration among local farmers. The system facilitates shared data access and cooperative water management practices, promoting a sense of community engagement and collective responsibility for resource stewardship.
4. **Resilience in Challenging Conditions:** Engineered with a focus on the region's specific challenges, such as potential water scarcity during certain months, the system exhibits resilience in the face of adversities. Its robust design ensures consistent operation even under challenging environmental conditions.
5. **Cultural and Environmental Integration:** Uniquely designed to integrate with the cultural and environmental aspects of the Machang Area, the system blends harmoniously with the local landscape. This integration not only showcases respect for the region's heritage but also minimizes disruption to the ecosystem.
6. **Adoption of Localized Crops:** Recognizing the diversity of crops cultivated in the Machang Area, the system supports the irrigation needs of various locally grown crops beyond rice. This adaptability encourages crop diversification, aligning with the changing demands of the local agricultural economy.

In conclusion, the dam irrigation system for the Machang Area not only addresses the broader challenges of water management but also encapsulates unique features tailored to the specific nuances of the region. Its localized adaptability, water conservation measures, community-driven elements, resilience, cultural integration, and support for diverse crops collectively contribute to its novelty and uniqueness in transforming agriculture in the Machang Area.

6. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL

Since our innovation mainly focuses on helping the farmers and community to solve their problem regarding the water system for their paddy fields. So in terms of potential commercialization, we do not focus directly on innovation, but mainly for corporate social responsibility (CSR) to solve the problems faced by them.

7. STATUS OF INNOVATION

In this innovative product, we use the conceptual process in coming up with ideas to assist the residents in obtaining water supply for the rice planting process. In this study we used the main source of water closest to the paddy planting area which can be taken with a distance of 2.5KM. Through this process, we will build a dam of water from the nearest rapids to collect water supply before being delivered using the underground piping system up to the paddy fields. This innovation process is very helpful for the residents in getting clean water supply for the process of planting paddy every year. This innovation process has also had a beneficial effect on the residents in obtaining a clean water supply for planting rice. We chose to innovate the pipe system because the terrain in the area is very helpful to us in transforming this innovation product to the people.

8. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the significance of efficient water management in agriculture cannot be overstated, especially as the global population continues to expand, and water resources face increasing competition and environmental challenges. As articulated in the literature, irrigated agriculture is expected to play a crucial role in meeting the rising demand for food. However, this reliance on irrigation must be coupled with sustainable and innovative approaches to water allocation and management. The conventional methods of irrigation have served their purpose, but the evolving landscape of water scarcity, climate change, and the need for resource optimization necessitate a paradigm shift in irrigation practices. The current challenges underscore the urgency of implementing smart watering techniques and modernized irrigation systems at the farm level. The innovation in irrigation technology, exemplified by the dam irrigation system, signifies a step towards addressing these challenges. By embracing precision, adaptability, and resource efficiency, this system represents a beacon of progress in agricultural water management. The ability to tailor water distribution to specific growth stages, adapt to environmental conditions, and integrate seamlessly with modern infrastructure positions it as a promising solution for the future.

The reports from experts such as Playán and Mateos (2006) highlight the importance of selecting appropriate irrigation systems and strategies based on a holistic understanding of water availability, climate, soil, and crop characteristics. The move towards supplemental irrigation during drought periods aligns with the contemporary need to mitigate water stress and enhance overall crop yields. Efforts to modernize water networks and irrigation systems globally reflect a collective acknowledgment of the pivotal role irrigation plays in food production and the sustainable use of water resources. The FAO's recognition that irrigation consumes a substantial portion of available freshwater emphasizes the critical need for increased efficiency in water use. The pursuit of initiatives to improve water use efficiency becomes imperative, especially in regions where water scarcity poses the greatest challenge to plant production. In essence, the journey towards sustainable water management and climate change adaptation in agriculture requires a concerted effort in embracing innovative irrigation technologies, refining irrigation scheduling approaches, and fostering a comprehensive understanding of local farming contexts. The dam irrigation system, with its smart features and environmental consciousness, stands as a testament to the ongoing commitment to achieving these goals. As we navigate the complexities of water availability and climate variability, the pursuit of advancements in irrigation technology remains pivotal for a resilient and productive agricultural future.

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